

Viscosity Measurement of Aqueous Solutions of Barium and Strontium Butyrates

R. P. VARMA* and ANIL KUMAR

Department of Chemistry, D. A. V. College, Muzaffarnagar-251 001

Manuscript received 17 May 1983, revised 30 September 1985, accepted 25 June 1986

Viscosity measurement of barium and strontium butyrates in water shows two critical micelle concentrations in dilute and concentration ranges. CMC (I) decreases but CMC (II) is independent of temperature. Viscosity data have been examined by Vand, Moulik and Jones-Dole equations. The parameters of these equations may be used to calculate the viscosity of soap solutions in the valid concentration range. The temperature dependence of fluidity of soaps has been studied by Arrhenius and Eyring's equations. The activation parameters of viscous flow, ΔH^* , ΔS^* and ΔG^* with respect to water have been evaluated which suggest the micelle formation in soap solutions.

PRESENCE of colloidal materials into a solvent causes an increase in viscosity which varies widely with nature of the solute. A considerable attention has been focussed¹⁻⁴ on the viscosity measurement of alkaline earth metal soaps of higher fatty acids ($>C_8$) in water to study their micellar behaviour mainly in dilute range of concentration. Since the properties of soap solutions vary in various regions of soap concentration⁵, no such investigations have been made so far for soaps of lower fatty acid ($<C_8$). In order to explore the viscosity behaviour of barium and strontium butyrates in water in the entire range of concentration at different temperatures (35–60°), the present study has been undertaken with a view to (i) determine the critical micelle concentration and study the effect of temperature, (ii) test the applicability of viscosity equations and (iii) calculate the thermodynamic parameters of viscous flow.

Experimental

AnalaR grade barium and strontium carbonates were used. n-Butyric acid (Sigma) was purified by distillation under reduced pressure. The procedure⁶ for the preparation of soap and measurement⁷ of viscosity of solutions is the same as reported earlier. Water needed for preparation of various solutions was prepared by distilling twice over alkaline $KMnO_4$.

Results and Discussion

Viscosity (η) increases with the increase in concentration and with the decrease in temperature of soap solutions (Table 1). The plot (Fig. 1) of η vs C (soap concentration) in dilute range is characterised by an intersection of two straight lines at CMC(I) which decreases with the increase

in temperature. In the concentrated range, the plots (Fig. 2) show the same nature but the CMC's (II) are independent of temperature. The second break in the plot, *i.e.* CMC(III) is due to formation of neutral colloid. The CMC(I) of barium soap is higher than strontium soap (Table 2).

The extrapolated values of viscosity, η_0 , for zero soap concentration is independent of nature of soap and are in complete agreement with the experimental values of water. This shows that soap molecules do not aggregate to an appreciable extent below CMC(I) whereas there is a marked change in the aggregation at CMC(II).

TABLE 1—VISCOSITY (MILLIPOISE) OF BARIUM AND STRONTIUM BUTYRATES IN WATER AT 35 AND 45°

Concn. of soap in mol dm ⁻³	Barium butyrate		Strontium butyrate	
	35°	45°	35°	45°
0.01	7.32	6.03	7.38	6.05
0.02	7.41	6.10	7.51	6.20
0.03	7.52	6.17	7.60	6.27
0.04	7.60	6.24	7.69	6.34
0.05	7.68	6.32	7.76	6.40
0.06	7.78	6.41	7.95	6.44
0.08	8.00	6.54	8.03	6.55
0.10	8.14	6.69	8.16	6.66
0.15	8.52	7.00	8.54	6.92
0.20	8.93	7.30	8.96	7.20
0.25	9.26	7.62	9.34	7.50
0.30	9.86	7.97	9.71	7.74
0.35	10.29	8.33	10.14	8.03
0.40	10.76	8.63	10.82	8.47
0.45	11.19	8.96	11.48	8.91
0.50	11.63	9.32	12.20	9.37
0.60	13.80	10.60	13.48	10.21
0.70	15.31	11.96	14.89	11.14
0.80	17.92	12.72	21.08	15.40

Fig. 1. Plot of viscosity (η , millipoise) vs concentration (C , mol dm^{-3}) of barium butyrate in water in dilute range 0.01–0.15 M at 35–60°.

Fig. 2. Plot of viscosity (η , millipoise) vs concentration (C , mol dm^{-3}) of barium butyrate in water in concentrated range 0.15–0.8 M at 35–60°.

where, Q and V are the interaction coefficient and molar volume of solute in $\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$.

Moulik⁹ :

$$(\eta/\eta_0)^2 = M + K^2 C^2 \quad (2)$$

where, M and K^2 are constants.

Jones–Dole¹⁰ :

$$\eta_{sp}/\sqrt{C} = A + B\sqrt{C} \quad (3)$$

where, the coefficients A and B refer to the soap and soap-solvent interaction, respectively.

The applicability of the viscosity equations (1, 2 and 3) has been tested from the linear plots of $1/C$ vs $1/\log(\eta/\eta_0)$, $(\eta/\eta_0)^2$ vs C^2 and η_{sp}/\sqrt{C} vs \sqrt{C} , respectively. Equations (1) and (2) are found valid in the concentration range above CMC(I). The viscosity parameters, V , Q , M and K^2 have been calculated (Table 3). These parameters can not be evaluated theoretically, therefore, graphical

TABLE 3—VISCOSITY PARAMETERS FOR BARIUM AND STRONTIUM BUTYRATES AT 35–60°

Temp. °C	Tested concn. limit mol dm^{-3}	Valid concn. range mol dm^{-3}	V	$-Q$	M	K^2
Barium butyrate						
35	0.01–0.8	0.3–0.5	0.52	1.44	1.47	4.5
40	0.01–0.8	0.3–0.5	0.47	1.06	1.44	4.3
45	0.01–0.8	0.25–0.5	0.45	0.77	1.43	4.0
50	0.01–0.8	0.25–0.5	0.42	0.72	1.38	3.8
55	0.01–0.8	0.25–0.5	0.37	0.26	1.34	3.7
60	0.01–0.8	0.25–0.5	0.34	0.13	1.30	3.6
Strontium butyrate						
35	0.01–0.8	0.04–0.3	0.67	3.85	1.28	5.8
40	0.01–0.8	0.08–0.4	0.57	3.84	1.24	5.6
45	0.01–0.8	0.08–0.2	0.52	3.83	1.22	4.8
50	0.01–0.8	0.04–0.3	0.47	3.81	1.20	4.4
55	0.01–0.8	0.04–0.2	0.38	3.26	1.18	4.0
60	0.01–0.8	0.05–0.2	0.35	2.91	1.16	3.8

testing has been performed. The evaluated parameters may be useful to calculate the viscosity of solutions. Molar volume (V) and the interaction coefficient ($-Q$) both decrease with increasing temperature. A comparison of the results shows that the strontium soap shows higher molar volume and lower interaction coefficient than barium soap. Moulik's constants also decrease with increase in temperature. Constant, M of barium soap is higher and K^2 lower than strontium soap. Jones–

TABLE 2—CMC (mol dm^{-3}) OF BARIUM AND STRONTIUM BUTYRATES IN DILUTE AND CONCENTRATED RANGES

Soap	Dilute range M	CMC (I) $\times 10^3$						Concentrate range M	CMC (II) M
		35°	40°	45°	50°	55°	60°		
Barium butyrate	0.01–0.15	10	9.5	9.0	8.4	6.6	6.0	0.15–0.80	0.50
Strontium butyrate	0.02–0.10	6.5	6.6	5.8	5.0	4.7	4.2	0.10–0.80	0.35

The viscosity data have been examined in the light of following equations.

Vand⁸ :

$$1/C = (0.921/V)^{-1} \cdot 1/\log(\eta/\eta_0) + QV \quad (1)$$

Dole plots are linear¹¹ in different concentrated ranges : I (0.01–0.15 M), II (0.15–0.5 M) and III (0.5–0.8 M). The intercepts and the slopes of the plots give, respectively, the coefficients

A and B which are given in Table 3. Constants $A(I)$, $A(II)$ and $B(I)$, $B(II)$ decrease with increase in temperature. The decrease in values of $A(I)$ and $A(II)$ with the rise in temperature is expected in view of more violent thermal agitation at higher temperatures and reduction of attractive forces. Constant $A(I)$ is lower than $A(II)$. This indicates that soap-soap interaction, *i.e.* micelle formation occurs above CMC. $A(II)$ values are all negative. Similar negative values of A have been observed^{1,2} at higher concentrations of solution of nickel and aluminium chlorides in ethanol. Further higher values of $B(I)$ than $B(II)$ shows that soap-solvent interaction is not favoured above CMC and soap-soap interaction predominates. Higher values of $A(I)$ and $A(II)$ and lower values of $B(I)$ and $B(II)$ of strontium soap shows that this soap has greater tendency to form micelle than barium soap which is further confirmed by its lower values of CMC (Table 1). It is interesting to point out that soap-solvent interaction of range III, $B(III)$ are higher than $B(II)$. This can be attributed to the fact that aggregation of the soap molecules beyond CMC of concentrated range boosts up the electrokinetic forces causing intake of solvent resulting in the increased viscosity of the system and thus of $B(III)$ values.

Fig. 3. Plots of ΔH° (kJ mol^{-1}), ΔS° ($\text{JK}^{-1} \text{mol}^{-1}$) and ΔG° (kJ mol^{-1}) vs concentration of soap (C): (\blacktriangle) strontium and (\bullet) barium.

The temperature dependence of $1/\eta$ has been evaluated in terms of Arrhenius and Eyring's equations^{1,3}. The variation of both the activation energy of viscous flow (ΔH^*) and entropy (ΔS^*) with concentration (Fig. 3) shows a little change below CMC. But above CMC there is an appreciable linear increase. ΔH^* measures energy barrier to fluid motion and increase in ΔH^* with concentration indicates less fluidity thus confirms

structured solvent and the micellar aggregation. The rapid increase in ΔH^* at higher concentration may be understood to have been due to structural change of micelle. Free energy of activation calculated from Gibb's equation controls the rate of flow in fluid process and the non-linear variation of $\Delta G-C$ plots (Fig. 3) below CMC(I) indicates the solute-solvent interaction as the principal kinetic entity^{1,4}. However, the plots are linear above CMC which confirms that no solute-solvent interaction occurs but soap forms micellar aggregation in the solution.

TABLE 4—VALUES OF A AND B OBTAINED FROM η_{sp}/\sqrt{C} vs \sqrt{C} IN DIFFERENT CONCENTRATION RANGES* OF BARIUM AND STRONTIUM BUTYRATE IN WATER AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES (35–60°)

Temp. °C	$A \times 10^3$			B		
	I	II	III	I	II	III
Barium butyrate						
35	-1.0	6.0	-186.0	1.40	1.14	3.84
40	-3.0	4.0	-163.0	1.38	1.10	3.44
45	-5.0	3.0	-127.0	1.35	1.06	2.89
50	-6.5	2.0	-115.0	1.33	1.02	2.68
55	-8.0	0.5	-93.0	1.30	1.01	2.34
60	-10.5	-2.0	-81.0	1.28	1.00	2.10
Strontium butyrate						
35	14.0	17.0	-71.0	1.10	0.80	2.30
40	12.0	16.0	-48.0	1.00	0.75	1.75
45	11.0	14.0	-43.0	0.90	0.70	1.70
50	8.0	9.0	-39.0	0.70	0.68	1.55
55	3.0	4.0	-37.0	0.60	0.65	1.50
60	2.0	3.0	-35.0	0.50	0.60	1.40

* I (0.01–0.15 M), II (0.15–0.5 M), III (0.5–0.8 M).

TABLE 5—SLOPES OF PLOTS OF ΔG AND ΔS vs TEMPERATURE OF SOAPS

Concn. range M	Barium butyrate		Strontium butyrate	
	$\frac{\partial \Delta G}{\partial T}$	$\frac{\partial \Delta S}{\partial T}$	$\frac{\partial \Delta G}{\partial T}$	$\frac{\partial \Delta S}{\partial T}$
0.01–0.1	-18.33	0.293	-18.83	0.293
0.15–0.5	-20.92	0.347	-23.01	0.335
0.5–0.8	-23.01	0.380	-25.10	0.356

The values of ΔG and ΔS decrease with the increase in temperature. The average values of the slopes of these parameters vs temperature are given in Table 5. A change in the slopes of free energy and entropy in the concentrated ranges of soaps confirms the micelle formation in the soap solutions.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Dr. K. N. Mehrotra for his keen interest throughout the work and the college authorities for providing facilities.

References

1. R. P. VARMA and P. BAHADUR, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1972, 10, 1189.

2. R. P. VARMA and P. BAHADUR, *Cellul. Chem. Technol.*, 1975, 9, 393.
3. R. P. VARMA and K. KUMAR, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1977, 54, 491.
4. R. P. VARMA and R. DAYAL, *Rev Roum. Chim.*, 1979, 24, 907.
5. J. W. MCBAIN, *J Phys Chem*, 1939, 43, 671.
6. R. P. VARMA and K. KUMAR, *Cellul. Chem. Technol.*, 1975, 9, 23.
7. R. P. VARMA and K. KUMAR, *J Am. Oil Chem Soc.*, 1977, 54, 156.
8. V. VAND, *J. Phys. Colloid Chem.*, 1948, 52, 277
9. S P MOULIK *J. Phys. Chem*, 1968, 72, 4682.
10. G. JONES and M. DOLE, *J Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 51, 2950.
11. K. N. MEHROTRA, V. P. MEHTA, M. HASAN and S. P. MATHUR, *Bull Soc. Chim Fr*, 1979, 54, 1.
12. F. E. DALIAN and H. T. BRISCOE, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1937, 41, 1129.
13. S. GLASSTONE, K. J. LAIDLER and H. EYRING, "Theory of Rate Process", McGraw-Hill, New York, 1941, p. 477.
14. J. C. MAC DONALD, J. SER PHILLIPS and J. J. GUERRERA, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1973, 77, 370.